

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NATURAL FIBERS REINFORCED POLY(LACTIC ACID) BASED BIOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Composites have played a pivotal role in a variety of applications. As a result of the increasing environmental awareness, the concern for environmental sustainability and the growing global waste problem is increased. Natural composites are gaining acceptance due to increasing environmental awareness, sustainability, and global waste problems. Manufacturing of high performance engineering materials from renewable resources is one ambitious goal currently pursued by researchers across the world. In the recent years, natural fibers have been increasingly used as alternative reinforcements in polymer composites due to their low cost, low density, environmental friendly and biodegradability [1-2].

As the production of fuel-derived plastics is often harmful to the environment. The waste disposal and recycling of commodity plastic are major issues worldwide. Thermoplastic materials reinforced with natural fibers are used in some sections of the automotive and construction industries, and these markets are rapidly expanding. Eco-friendly biocomposites from plant-derived fiber (natural/biofiber) and crop-derived polymer (biopolymer) are novel materials and would be of great importance to the materials world. Biopolymers are now moving into mainstream use, and may soon be competing with commodity plastics. Bio polyesters such as poly (lactic acid) (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) are attracting attention as promising biopolymers. PLA is a highly versatile biopolymer and is highlighted because it is derived from a renewable resource such as corn [3]. PLA can be processed by injection molding, blow molding, and film forming because the glass-transition temperature (T_g) of PLA is 54°C and the melting temperature (T_m) is 172°C [4-5]. Although

PLA has mechanical properties suited for industrial plastic application. However, as the brittleness problem of PLA, it requires modification for more practical applications. The improvement of the impact properties of PLA is an addition of fillers or reinforcement materials. The quality of the fiber-matrix interface is significant for the application of natural fibers as reinforcement for polymer matrices. The coupling agent serves as chemical bridge between the reinforcement and matrix resin. A variety of silanes have been applied as coupling agents in the natural fiber reinforced polymer composites to promote interfacial adhesion and improve the properties of composite [6-7]. There are some research works studied about the using of thermosetting resin as the surface treatment for natural fiber to enhance the thermal stability during high temperature process. The using of flexible epoxy resin coating on natural fiber improved the mechanical properties and also thermal stability of natural fiber reinforced polymer composite [8-9]. In addition, the impact strength can be increased by providing flexible interphase regions in the composite or by using impact modifiers. The flexible epoxy resin is considered to be the surface modification for enhancing the mechanical properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites.

Many research works have been studied the utilization of natural renewable resources as the reinforcement in polymer composites [10-15]. Natural fibers are further subdivided into whether they came from plants, animals or minerals. The purpose of this study was to examine the potential reinforcing effect of short, randomly oriented natural fibers on PLA. In this study, both plant and animal source reinforcement such as bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber, coconut fiber and silk fiber were selected

as the abundant natural resource in Thailand. The effects of flexible epoxy surface treatment on mechanical properties of different reinforcement PLA based biocomposites were investigated.

2 Materials and Experimental

2.1 Materials

Poly (lactic acid) (PLA : TE-2000C, Unitika plastic, Japan) was used as a matrix resin. The natural reinforcement consisting of bamboo fiber (BF), silk fiber (SF), vetiver grass fiber (VF) and coconut fiber (CCF) (all material obtained from Thailand without any pre-sizing) were selected as the reinforcement for PLA. The characteristic of natural reinforcement was shown in Table 1. Flexible epoxy resin (Epoxidized polybutadiene, EPOLEAD PB 3600, Daicel chemical Co.Ltd., Japan) was used as surface treatment for the natural fibers.

Table 1. Mechanical and physical characteristic of selected natural fibers.

Fiber	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Density (g/cm ³)	Aspect ratio
Bamboo fiber (BF)	35.9	441	0.80	9.5
Vetiver grass fiber (VF)	12.0-49.8	247-723	1.50	3.8
Coconut fiber (CCF)	4.0-6.0	131-175	1.10	26.0
Silk fiber (SF)	12.0-17.0	610-690	1.17	1.7

2.2 Surface treatment of natural fibers

The flexible epoxy resin (1 wt.% of reinforcement) was dissolved in acetone (1 g resin : 200 ml acetone) for reducing the viscosity prior treatment process. The treated reinforcements were natural dried at room temperature for 24 hours and then vacuum dried at 80°C for 24 hours in order to remove acetone.

2.3 Specimens preparation

The reinforcement and PLA were dried in hot air oven at 85°C for 16 hours prior to compounding

with PLA matrix by using twin screw extruder (JSW TEX30HSS) at 180°C. The standard dumbbell shape specimens were fabricated by injection molding (TOYO TI-30F6) at injection temperature 210°C. The content of bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber and coconut fiber were varied from 10, 20, 30 and 40 wt.%, respectively. However, in silk fiber case, the fiber content was varied from 5 and 10 wt.% which the maximum loading content was limited at 10 wt.% due to the troubleshooting during compounding process as shown in Fig. 1. The maximum calculated volume fraction of bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber, coconut fiber and silk fiber were 50.6, 35.3, 42.7 and 10.5 vol.%, respectively.

Fig. 1. The troubleshooting during compounding of silk fiber/PLA pellet.

2.4 Testing

Tensile test (ASTM D638) was conducted on an Instron universal testing machine (Instron 4206) with a testing speed 1 mm/min. The gauge length was 115 mm. Izod impact test (ASTM D256) was performed on the Digital Impact tester (Toyoseiki) with 5.5 J pendulum. The V-notch shape with 2 mm deep was prepared. At least five specimens were repeated.

2.5 Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM 5200) was conducted on the fracture surface of the tensile tested specimen to examine the failure surface and failure behavior. The samples were mounted on aluminum holders and gold sputtered for 6 minutes prior observation.

3 Results and Discussion

The tensile modulus and tensile strength of the PLA based biocomposites with different natural fiber are shown in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The neat PLA has a tensile modulus of 3.52 GPa and tensile strength 52.74 MPa. As presented in Table 2, the

addition of natural fibers improved the modulus of PLA as the results of addition of high stiffness material. It can be seen that the tensile modulus of untreated bamboo fiber composite was higher than other natural fibers. This effect was due to the different in mechanical properties of each fiber and also the different in size and shape, which related to the fiber characteristics as shown in Table 1.

Table 2. Tensile modulus of the composites

Fiber content (wt.%)	Tensile modulus (GPa)			
	BF	VF	CCF	SF
0	3.52 (±0.26)	3.52 (±0.26)	3.52 (±0.26)	3.52 (±0.26)
5	-	-	-	3.94 (±0.10)
10	4.73 (±0.40)	4.09 (±0.17)	4.60 (±0.20)	4.28 (±0.24)
20	5.89 (±0.22)	5.08 (±0.22)	4.94 (±0.31)	-
30	7.36 (±0.31)	5.89 (±0.17)	5.50 (±0.14)	-
40	9.77 (±0.42)	6.55 (±0.26)	6.12 (±0.23)	-

However, the tensile strength of PLA biocomposites did not show the improvement when compared with neat PLA. The tensile strengths of vetiver grass fiber/PLA, coconut fiber/PLA and silk fiber/PLA decreased when the reinforcement content increased. However, it can also be seen in Table 3 that the addition of bamboo fiber up to 30 wt.% did not show the reduction of tensile strength. This was due to that bamboo fiber has higher fiber strength than other natural fibers. In addition, the bonding between different natural fiber and PLA matrix were different. From SEM micrograph of fracture surface, in Figs. 2(b), 2(c) and 2(d) show evidence of the poor interfacial adhesion between vetiver grass fiber, coconut fiber and silk fiber and with PLA, respectively. This poor interfacial bonding results in poor stress transfer from PLA matrix to the reinforcing fibers. Moreover, the reduction of tensile strengths of coconut fiber/PLA composite becomes severe with the increasing of fiber content. A possible explanation of this can be due to agglomeration of coconut fiber. On the other hand, the tensile strength of bamboo fiber/PLA composites almost remain constant with increasing fiber content and only slightly decrease at 40 wt.% fiber loading. The fiber-matrix interface in the bamboo fiber/PLA

composites from the Fig. 2(a) shows better adhesion bonding than other reinforcement that results in remains constant strength.

Table 3. Tensile strength of the composites

Fiber content (wt.%)	Tensile strength (MPa)			
	BF	VF	CCF	SF
0	52.74 (±0.41)	52.74 (±0.41)	52.74 (±0.41)	52.74 (±0.41)
5	-	-	-	49.66 (±1.19)
10	51.89 (±0.40)	48.82 (±0.58)	50.89 (±2.16)	36.40 (±1.79)
20	53.28 (±0.64)	48.11 (±0.32)	50.10 (±0.78)	-
30	52.69 (±1.37)	43.96 (±1.24)	46.54 (±1.32)	-
40	49.39 (±1.46)	36.36 (±1.72)	29.13 (±1.83)	-

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of the untreated PLA biocomposites: a) bamboo fiber/PLA, b) vetiver grass fiber/PLA, c) coconut fiber/PLA and d) silk fiber/PLA.

The notched Izod impact strength results for the tested composites are shown in Table 4. The impact strength of neat PLA was 2.05 kJ/m² and the impact strength of the composite decreased with the presence of natural reinforcements. This indicated that the addition of natural reinforcement was ineffective to improve the brittleness of PLA. The reduction of impact strength of the composites resulted from the poor interfacial adhesion between reinforcement and matrix. It is known that the interfacial bonding strength are strongly influenced the impact properties of composite materials. Impact energy is dissipated by debonding, fiber and/or matrix fracture and fiber pull out. This was already

revealed by SEM micrograph in Fig. 2, which shows that the interfacial bonding of bamboo fiber/PLA composite was the best among all studied reinforcements.

Table 4. Notched Izod impact strength of the composites

Fiber content (wt.%)	Notched Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)			
	BF	VF	CCF	SF
0	2.05 (±0.35)	2.05 (±0.35)	2.05 (±0.35)	2.05 (±0.35)
5	-	-	-	1.84 (±0.05)
10	1.76 (±0.07)	1.87 (±0.01)	1.76 (±0.14)	1.64 (±0.14)
20	1.77 (±0.01)	1.62 (±0.14)	1.63 (±0.08)	-
30	1.75 (±0.07)	1.55 (±0.12)	1.23 (±0.06)	-
40	1.56 (±0.10)	1.49 (±0.10)	0.90 (±0.10)	-

Fig. 3. SEM images of the surface of natural reinforcements compared between untreated, acetone washed and flexible epoxy treated.

The surfaces of natural reinforcement treated with flexible epoxy resin are shown in Fig. 3. Since acetone reduces the viscosity of flexible epoxy resin, the effect of acetone washing on the surface of reinforcement was investigated. Immersed acetone reinforcement surfaces are shown in Fig. 3. The figure shows that acetone removed the waxes and impurities on the reinforcement surfaces. After the surface treatment by flexible epoxy resin, The flexible epoxy resin modified surfaces are also captured in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. Tensile modulus of untreated and treated natural fiber reinforced PLA composites (a) bamboo fiber, (b) vetiver grass fiber, (c) coconut fiber and (d) silk fiber.

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Fig. 5. Tensile strength of untreated and treated natural fiber reinforced PLA composites (a) bamboo fiber, (b) vetiver grass fiber, (c) coconut fiber and (d) silk fiber.

Fig. 6. Impact energy of untreated and treated natural fiber reinforced PLA composites (a) bamboo fiber, (b) vetiver grass fiber, (c) coconut fiber and (d) silk fiber.

Fig. 4. Showed how the influence of the flexible epoxy surface treatment affected the tensile modulus of natural fiber reinforced PLA composites. It was found that the flexible epoxy surface treatment reduced the tensile modulus of bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber and silk fiber reinforced PLA composites. The reduction of tensile modulus may due to the coating of natural fiber surfaces with the flexible material, which reduced the stiffness of natural fibers. However the tensile modulus of untreated and treated coconut fiber reinforced PLA composite behaved differently.

The effects of flexible epoxy treatment on tensile strength of PLA biocomposites were presented in Fig. 5. The tensile strength of treated bamboo fiber, coconut fiber and silk fiber reinforced PLA composites were higher than the untreated composites. The improvement in tensile strength was believed to be due to the better interfacial adhesion between natural fiber and PLA matrix with the flexible epoxy treatment. On the other hand the effect of flexible epoxy on tensile strength of vetiver grass fiber/PLA composite was different when compared with other natural fibers. The flexible epoxy treated vetiver grass fiber/PLA composite showed less improvement in tensile strength when compared with other reinforcements.

The impact strength of untreated and flexible epoxy treated bamboo fiber reinforced PLA composites at different fiber content was shown in Fig. 6(a). It was found that the impact strength of flexible epoxy treated composites were higher than the untreated composites. In addition, the flexible epoxy treated bamboo fiber at fiber content 40 % by weight showed the impact strength improvement when compared with neat PLA matrix. The flexible epoxy surface treatment also improved the impact property of coconut fiber and silk fiber reinforced PLA composites as shown in Figs. 6(c)-(d). However, the impact strength of treated coconut fiber and silk fiber reinforced PLA composites was lower than the value of neat PLA matrix. On the other hand, the effect of flexible epoxy surface treatment on the impact strength of vetiver grass fiber reinforced PLA composites was indistinguishable when compared with an untreated composite as observed in Fig. 6(b). It can be seen that the effects of flexible epoxy treated on the impact strength improvement were dependent on the type of reinforcement.

The interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix played an important role for the mechanical property of fiber reinforced composites. The SEM

micrographs of fracture surface compared between untreated and flexible epoxy treated composites of three different natural fibers are shown in Fig. 7. The layer of flexible epoxy resin formed on the surfaces between natural fiber and matrix after treatment as the flexible interphase is illustrated in Fig. 8. The interfacial structure to be formed on fiber surface was not layer but “phase” with thickness was established. The unclear interface between flexible interphase and matrix were formed and called “Thick and Gradient Interphase”. This flexible gradient interphase can interrupted the debonding and cracks propagation between fiber/matrix interfaces, which was reported by Yoshikawa et al. [16]. However, in this study the gradient interface between PLA matrix and flexible epoxy interphase was not clearly observed.

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of fracture surface of a) untreated-, b) treated-bamboo fiber/PLA, c) untreated-, d) treated-vetiver grass fiber/PLA, e) untreated-, f) treated-coconut fiber/PLA, g) untreated-, h) treated-silk fiber/PLA.

The interfacial adhesion between fiber/interphase and interphase/matrix were the important factors for the effectiveness of flexible interphase on mechanical property improvement. It can be seen that at the surface of treated bamboo fiber, coconut

fiber and silk fiber in Figs. 7(b), 7(f) and 7(h), respectively, small amount of flexible epoxy resin can be observed on the surfaces of the fibers. Good adhesion between reinforcing fiber and flexible epoxy interphase resulted in tensile strength improvement of bamboo fiber and coconut fiber reinforced PLA composites. However, in case of treated vetiver grass fiber in Fig. 7(d), no flexible epoxy resin appeared on the fiber surfaces. It can be assumed that the interfacial bonding between flexible resin and PLA was constant with different natural fibers. These two different interfacial adhesions resulted in the different fracture mechanism when comparing treated vetiver grass fiber reinforced PLA composite with other reinforcements. It is possible to note that the interfacial adhesion between vetiver grass fiber and flexible interphase was weaker than the interfacial bonding between flexible interphase and PLA matrix. The weak bonding of vetiver grass fiber and flexible epoxy resin resulted in slightly different tensile strength improvement versus other natural fibers.

Fig. 8. The schematic illustration of “Thick and Gradient Interphase” concept of flexible interphase treated fiber and matrix

The tensile modulus and tensile strength improvement performance of untreated composites were compared with flexible epoxy resin treated composites in Figs. 9-12. The comparison was obtained from the differential ratio in percentage of the tensile properties at 40 % by weight natural fiber content and in reference to the properties of PLA matrix. The tensile modulus of bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber and silk fiber reinforced PLA composites

were strongly affected by flexible epoxy surface treatment. On the other hand, the modulus of coconut fiber/PLA composite was unaltered by the coating of flexible epoxy interphase as shown in Fig. 11. Among all reinforcement bamboo fiber was the most effective reinforcement to enhance the tensile strength of PLA as shown in Fig. 9. Moreover, by using the flexible epoxy resin as the surface treatment for bamboo fiber the tensile strength of PLA can be improved significantly.

Fig. 9. Performance comparison between untreated and flexible epoxy treated bamboo fiber/PLA composites.

Fig. 10. Performance comparison between untreated and flexible epoxy treated vetiver grass fiber/PLA composites.

Fig. 11. Performance comparison between untreated and flexible epoxy treated coconut fiber/PLA composites.

Fig. 12. Performance comparison between untreated and flexible epoxy treated silk fiber/PLA composites.

4 Conclusions

The PLA based biocomposite reinforced with different natural reinforcement consisting of bamboo fiber, vetiver grass fiber, coconut fiber and silk fiber and were prepared. The maximum loading content of silk fiber was limited at 10 wt.% due to compounding process issues. The addition of natural reinforcements improved tensile modulus of PLA as the result of addition of high stiffness material. However, the tensile strength and Izod impact strength of PLA biocomposites decreased when the reinforcement content increases. The poor interfacial bonding results in poor stress transfer from PLA matrix to the reinforcements. Moreover, the reduction of mechanical strengths of composite becomes severe with the increasing of fiber content due to reinforcement agglomerations.

The effects of flexible epoxy surface treatment on tensile properties and Izod impact strength of biocomposites were evaluated. Tensile modulus of composites decreased with the using of flexible epoxy surface treatment. The tensile strength and Izod impact strength of flexible epoxy treated composites were higher than the untreated composites. The improvement in mechanical strength resulted from the improvement of interfacial between reinforcement and PLA matrix. However, it can be seen that the flexible epoxy treatment depended on the reinforcement. By introducing this treatment better mechanical properties were obtained with the exception of the vetiver grass fiber/PLA combination, which remained nearly the same. Bamboo fiber proved to be the most effective reinforcement.

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